

Chemical Investigation of *Clerodendron fragrans*

PAHUP SINGH and (Mrs.) C. L. SINGHI

Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan,
Jaipur-302 004

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GENUS *Clerodendron* (Verbenaceae) consists of small trees or shrubs. The roots of *Clerodendron* have anthelmintic¹ and antibacterial² properties and are reported to cure serofulous, venereal infection³, bronchitis asthma, ozocana, fevers, diseases of blood⁴, stomach troubles, syphilis and gonorrhoea⁵.

A perusal of literature reveals that no work has been reported on the stem and roots of *C. fragrans*, however, some work has been reported on its leaves⁶. The present investigation on the roots and stem of above plant reveals the isolation and characterisation of various constituents.

Experimental

Dried and coarsely powdered roots and stem were exhaustively extracted with hot light petrol (60-80°) and methanol successively. The extract was concentrated under reduced pressure. The light petroleum extract was chromatographed over silica gel using the solvents of increasing polarity and yielded triacontane, α -amyrin, β -sitosterol, (24 S) ethylcholesta-5,22,25 trienes-3- β -ol, clerosterol, β -sitosterol- β -D glucoside from light petroleum extract and clerodolone from methanol extract respectively.

Results and Discussion

Triacontane: Pure light petrol fraction gave white solid m.p. 64°, $C_{30}H_{62}$; M^+ 422, crystallised from benzene as white granules, and was identified as triacontane.

(24 S) **Ethylcholesta-5, 22, 25 triene-3- β -ol**: Elution with light petrol-benzene (1:1) yielded white shining crystals, m.p. 144-5°, $C_{28}H_{46}O$; M^+ 410 and responded to Liebermann-Burchard and Noller tests. Its identification was further confirmed by Co-TLC, m.m.p. with an authentic sample and through the preparation of its acetate (Ac_2O/py), m.p. 140° and benzoate ($PhCOCl$) m.p. 136°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 38^\circ$.

α -Amyrin: Light petrol-benzene (1:2) eluted fractions afforded a white compound, m.p. 185-86°, $C_{30}H_{50}O$; M^+ 426 responded to Noller and Liebermann-Burchard test for triterpenoids. Its ir spectrum showed ν_{max}^{KB} ; cm^{-1} 3350 (O-H stretch) 2990-2855 (C-H stretch), 1640 (C=C stretch) 1475 (CH_2 bending). Its identity was further confirmed by Co-TLC, m.m.p., Co-IR with an authentic sample and by the preparation of its acetate, m.p. 222-23°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 83^\circ$.

β -Sitosterol: Elution with pure benzene gave colourless flakes of β -sitosterol m.p. 135-36°, $C_{28}H_{48}O$, acetate m.p. 124-25° and benzoate m.p. 143-44°.

Clerosterol: Elution with benzene yielded white needles m.p. 145-46°, $C_{28}H_{46}O$; M^+ 412. It responded to Liebermann-Burchard and Noller tests. It gave deep red colour in Salkowski test and showed prominent peaks at 3450-3230 (O-H stretch), 1640 (C=CH₂ stretch), 890, 960 and 800 cm^{-1} . The identity was confirmed by Co-TLC, m.m.p., with an authentic sample. Its acetate m.p. 141° (reported m.p. 142°)^{8,9} was readily formed. It had $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 50^\circ$.

β -Sitosterol- β -D-glucoside: Elution with benzene ethyl acetate (1:1) fraction furnished white coloured crystals, m.p. 284-85°, $C_{50}H_{80}O_6$. It responded to Liebermann-Burchard test. It also gave Molisch's test thereby indicating its glycosidic nature. It showed peaks at 3400 (O-H stretch), 1640 cm^{-1} (-C=C stretch), and 1150-1060 cm^{-1} (C-O-C linkage) indicating that compound to be glucoside of sterol.

Compound was hydrolysed with 7% sulphuric acid and a glycone, a white compound, m.p. 136-37° was identified as β -sitosterol by Co-TLC and m.m.p. Sugar was identified as glucoside by Copaper chromatography with an authentic sample of D-glucoside. It was further confirmed by Co. tic m.m.p. with an authentic sample.

Clerodolone: Methanolic extract on standing in refrigerator and washing with cold petroleum ether furnished, colourless compound which was crystallised from methanol-water as white needles. m.p. 288-89° (dec) $C_{20}H_{34}O_8$, M^+ 456. Ir spectrum showed important peaks at 3425 (O-H stretch), 1680 (C=O stretch), 1640 (-C=C stretch), supported by another band at 885 non-conjugated double bond. It readily formed acetate, m.p. 267-68° (reported 270-72°)^{9,10}. Its identity was further confirmed by Co-TLC, m.m.p. with an authentic sample, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 21$.

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**A Preliminary Note on the Activity of
Diospyros montana Bark Extract on Ehrlich
Ascites carcinoma in Mice**

BANASRI HAZRA*, PRATIMA SUR*, BIMANESH SUR**
AMALENDU BANERJEE** and DURLOV K. ROY*

* Department of Pharmacy and ** Department of Chemistry,
Jadavpur University, Calcutta-700 032

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THE stem bark of *Diospyros montana* Roxb. has been said to be useful in treatment of tumours¹. Since no systematic investigation to establish its anti-tumour activity has been reported so far, it was decided to study the action of *D. montana* bark extract on Ehrlich Ascites Carcinoma (E.A.C.) as the tumour model with Swiss Albino mice as its host. A preliminary attempt has also been made to study the haematological parameters of the mice treated with the crude extract with respect to the control.

Experimental

Materials and methods: Stem bark of *D. montana* was dried and powdered. An extract of the dried powder was prepared with 90% ethanol followed by removal of the solvent in vacuo, whereupon a dark-coloured solid was obtained (C.P.). E.A.C. was routinely maintained in male Swiss A mice. They were always fed with fixed standard mice diet and water *ad libitum*. Two groups of mice (18-20 g), six of them in each group, were inoculated i.p. with 1.8×10^5 E.A.C. cells (washed and viable) as done previously². Daily treatment of one group (E) with a solution of C.P. in propylene glycol was started 24 hrs after implantation, while the control group (C) was injected with the same volume of the vehicle only (0.05 ml of propylene glycol). LD₅₀ value for the C.P. was found to be 800 mg/kg (i.p.) in male Swiss A mice. The experimental group was treated with 200 mg/kg/day of C.P.³ intraperitoneally for sixteen consecutive days. Another group (A), containing six normal healthy mice (18-20 g) was treated with 200 mg/kg/day of C.P. in propylene glycol in the same way and for the same period. All the groups of mice were observed and weighed regularly. Survival of all the groups were recorded. The growth of tumour was found out as measured weight minus initial weight

* Address for correspondence :
Dr. (Mrs) Pratima Sur, Research Associate, Department of Pharmacy, Jadavpur University, Calcutta-700 032.

of each mouse in g⁴. A comparative picture of the growth of tumour in E-group with respect to that in C-group for first twenty days has been shown in Fig. 1. The inhibition of growth was statistically evaluated by Student's t-test. The increase of the life span of E-group of animal over the C-group was calculated as done previously⁵ using the formula :

$$\text{Increases in life span} = \left(\frac{\text{Survival time of treated group}}{\text{Survival time of untreated group}} - 1 \right) \times 100$$

For haematological study, comparison was made amongst three groups of mice (18-20 g) on the 20th day after tumour transplantation on the E- and C-groups. The first group (N-) comprised of six normal healthy mice, the second group being the mice survived in E-group (five out of six) and the third group consisted of the mice surviving in C-group (four out of six). Blood was taken from the tip of the tail of each mouse and counted for

Fig. 1. Effect of *Diospyros montana* bark extract on tumour growth after the inoculum of 1.8×10^5 E.A.C. cells in Swiss mice. Tumour growth, expressed as weight increase in mice above their initial weight, is plotted against the number of days. Each point represents the mean of weight increase of six mice \pm S.E. —○— Experimental ; —●— Control. *P<0.05, **P<0.001. (Student's t-test).

total R.B.C. and total W.B.C. using cell-diluting fluids and hemocytometer⁶. Differential count of W.B.C. was done with Leishman stain. The results have been given in Table 1 and Fig. 2 respectively.

TABLE 1—R. B. C. AND W. B. C. COUNTS OF MICE TREATED WITH *D. montana* EXTRACT AS COMPARED TO NORMAL MICE

Test Group	R. B. C. Count ($\times 10^6/cm^3$)	W. B. C. Count ($\times 10^6/cm^3$)
Normal Mice (N)	9.35 \pm 0.25	9.76 \pm 0.29
Control Mice (C)	9.26 \pm 0.41†	21.58 \pm 0.66*
Experimental Mice (E)	8.59 \pm 0.32†	11.02 \pm 1.06†

*P<0.001, †P>0.05, as per Student's t-test.